

18TH INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON CHEMISTRY AND THE ENVIRONMENT

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11 – 15 JUNE 2023 VENICE, ITALY

Venue:

SCIENTIFIC CAMPUS

CA' FOSCARI UNIVERSITY OF VENICE (ITALY)

Book of Abstracts

Dear colleagues,

On behalf of the Executive Board of the European Chemical Society, I wish you a warm welcome to this 18th International Conference on Chemistry and the Environment. The European Chemical Society – in short EuChemS – is an overarching society at the European level with over 50 national member societies as members. In this way, EuChemS represents approximately 130,000 chemists from all over Europe. Did you ever realize that by being a member of your national society, you are a member of EuChemS too?

The slogan of this conference is 'Towards a pollution free society', which is well aligned with activities from EuChemS. The European Commission recently set up the Zero Pollution Stakeholder Platform and EuChemS was invited to join. The platform will effectively mainstream the zero pollution agenda by bringing together stakeholders and experts of different policy areas, including health, agriculture, research and innovation, transport, digitalization and the environment. EuChemS will emphasize to address the Zero Pollution challenges from the chemistry perspective in a science-based approach.

I am here in the Netherlands, but you are in the beautiful city of Venice, that I am sure will inspire you to have fruitful and constructive discussions on how to get to zero pollution and how to address many other challenges to create a sustainable environment. I wish you a very enjoyable conference!

Floris Rutjens

President of the European Chemical Society (EuChemS)

Triclosan and its Metabolites as Potential Thyroid-Disrupting Chemicals: In Silico Analysis

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Triclosan is a synthetic antimicrobial agent used in disinfectants, cosmetic products, clothing textiles, and other materials. Studies suggest the bioaccumulation potential of triclosan in the environment and thus exposure to triclosan emerged concerns about the possible adverse effects of both parent compound and its metabolites on the endocrine system. The aim of this study was to conduct in silico analysis in order to evaluate if triclosan and its 4 metabolites could be classified as thyroid-disrupting chemicals, considering their binding affinity for thyroid receptors, and molecular and pharmacokinetic properties. Interaction between the analyzed compounds and thyroid receptor alpha (TRalpha; PDB entry code: 1NAV), beta (TRbeta; PDB entry code: 1NAX), and thyroxine-binding globulin (TBG; PDB entry code: 4X30) was determined using GOLD molecular docking tool. Molecular and pharmacokinetic properties were analyzed using SwissADME and admetSAR online tools. Regarding the molecular descriptors, for triclosan and its metabolites, polar surface area was in the range 18.46-49.69 Å², molecular weight 295-315 g/mol, number of rotatable bonds 2-4, number of hydrogen bond acceptors (NHBA) < 4 and number of hydrogen bond donors (NHBD) < 3. Lipophilicity, determined as logP was in the range 3.55-4.68, which indicated good oral bioavailability. Based on the pharmacokinetic analysis, good Caco-2 permeability and penetration via blood-brain barrier could be expected. Binding affinities of the analyzed compounds, using ChemPLP fitness scores, were in the range 69.01-77.77 (co-crystallized ligand affinity-88.89), 55.76-63.15 (co-crystallized ligand affinity-99.00), and 49.86-64.38 (co-crystallized ligand affinity-81.72), for TRalpha, TRbeta, and TBG, respectively. The highest score for TRbeta was observed for triclosan (63.15), while monohydroxylated metabolites showed the highest scores for TRalpha and TBG (77.77 and 65.38, respectively). In compared with the obtained ChemPLP fitness scores for bisphenol A (TRalpha-66.50, TRbeta-65.37, TBG-59.66) the obtained results suggest that triclosan and its metabolites may impair thyroid function.

Acknowledgement

This work was supported by the Provincial Secretariat for Higher Education and Scientific Research, AP Vojvodina, Republic of Serbia [Grant number 142-451- 3120/2022-01].

References

Milanović, M., et al. (2023) Comprehensive insight into triclosan-from widespread occurrence to health outcomes. *Environ Sci Pollut Res Int.* 10, p.25119-25140. doi: 10.1007/s11356-021-17273-0.